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FACTSHEET
DELIVERABLE 4.5: IPM STRATEGIES OF 25
NCC'S

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IPM STRATEGIES OF 25 NCC'S

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SUMMARY

Deliverable 4.5 contains 25 reports which describe exemplary Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies for every case study within the SUPPORT project, by relying on the IPM inventory that was provided in [Deliverable 1.1](#) of the project. The crops that are being studied within SUPPORT are: wheat, maize, onion, potato, strawberry, apple, wine grape and olive.

FIGURE 1: THE 25 CASE STUDIES WITHIN THE SUPPORT PROJECT, INCLUDING THE EUROPEAN COVERAGE (%) OF THE CROP AREAS IN THE MEMBER STATES OF THE SUPPORT CONSORTIUM.

The aim is to combine the individual IPM tools from Deliverable 1.1 into complete crop protection strategies, for a selected reference year with typical market conditions and average levels of biotic and abiotic stress. This is done for all 25 National Crop Clusters (NCCs) within the project. A typical IPM strategy represents a crop protection strategy applied on a farm of average size during an average year concerning biotic stress (pest and disease pressure and damage), abiotic stress (weather conditions) and market situation.

SUMMARY (CONTINUED)

For some NCCs, it was not possible to describe one typical IPM strategy, because of the use of different cultivation systems or significant regional differences in the country due to climatic or environmental features. Therefore, each NCC leader was asked to select, in consultation with local crop specialists, at minimum one, and at maximum five production systems/geographic regions within the NCC for which an IPM strategy should be defined and analysed. Every IPM strategy consists of two scenarios: one that is representative for the majority of the farmers (state-of-the-art scenario) and one that is being used by a minority of farmers who are more sustainability oriented (IPM improved scenario). All data were collected using desktop research and expert consultation.

By summarising representative IPM scenarios, Deliverable 4.5 serves as a guide for discussing IPM tools and scenarios with individual farmers or groups. In addition, it provides a starting point for further in-depth impact analysis of the IPM strategies using the IPM monitoring tool developed within the SUPPORT project. This way, the deliverable acts as a source of inspiration, encouraging farmers and advisors to adopt alternative, more sustainable IPM tools in a well-informed manner. This enables the development of IPM strategies that reduce pesticide use and the impact of crop protection on health and the environment, while addressing climate change and regulatory challenges.

KEY RESULTS

- Deliverable 1.1 of the SUPPORT project created an IPM inventory (M.D. Thorsted, S. Appel & J.E. Jensen, 2024), providing an overview of the different IPM tools that can be used in the cultivation of the eight crops that are being investigated within the project. Deliverable 4.5 combines these IPM tools into complete crop protection strategies for each NCC.
- None of the NCCs reported region-specific differences in crop protection, therefore, only the different cropping systems were taken into account when constructing the crop protection strategies. For each cropping system, two scenarios were drafted, one that is representative for the majority of the farmers (state-of-the-art scenario) and one that is being used by a minority of farmers who are more sustainability oriented (IPM improved scenario).
- For every state-of-the-art and IPM improved scenario, an overview of the number of IPM tools included in the scenario is given, with a distinction made between preventive, monitoring and intervention tools, as well as an overview of the number of used pesticide products.
- For all IPM strategies, the two scenarios (state-of-the-art and IPM improved scenario) were compared. This revealed that, in general, a wider variety of IPM tools is being applied in the IPM improved scenarios compared to the state-of-the-art scenarios. Consequently, the additional actions that are being implemented by farmers in order to reduce the use of synthetic pesticides require extra efforts from them, such as more labour time and extra know-how on the additional measures.
- The most common tools that are included in the IPM improved scenarios are: additional monitoring and scouting of pests and diseases, longer crop rotations, optimising sowing/planting conditions, field/crop hygiene, the use of beneficials or natural enemies and mechanical weed control. Longer crop rotations were mentioned in the IPM improved strategies of potato, onion, maize (only Denmark, not Romania and Switzerland) and wheat (only Denmark and Germany, not Romania and Switzerland).

KEY RESULTS

- The use of natural enemies is also already mentioned in the state-of-the-art scenarios of high density apple orchards in the Netherlands, Poland and Italy, strawberry cultivation in the Netherlands and Belgium and organic wheat cultivation in Romania.
- Detailed information and visual representations of the crop protection strategies of each NCC can be found in the annexes of the deliverable

FIGURE 2: EXAMPLE OF THE VISUAL REPRESENTATION OF A CROP PROTECTION STRATEGY (FLEMISH STATE-OF-THE-ART SCENARIO AND IPM IMPROVED SCENARIO FOR STORAGE POTATOES).

CROP SPECIFIC INFORMATION

For detailed information about the crop protection strategies in each country, please consult to the crop specific sections in [Deliverable 4.5](#).

Winegrape, olive, apple

Winegrape and olive generally require overall the lowest number of pesticides, particularly in low-density orchards. Because of the perennial nature of winegrape, olive and apple, there is a big focus on healthy plant material, hygiene of the crop/on the field and stimulation of natural habitats for beneficials. Also noticeable is the fact that in **apple** production, biostimulants are already commonly used to increase plant resilience and stimulate nutrient uptake.

Maize, wheat

Cereal crops strongly differ regarding disease pressure: in **maize**, no fungicides are used since weeds are the main problem and, therefore, the focus of the intervention measures. **Wheat** production on the other hand, has to deal with fungal diseases. Because of the high weed pressure in maize, mechanical weed control is already part of the state-of-the-art scenarios in Romania and Switzerland (not yet in Denmark). In wheat, this is also the case for Switzerland, however, mechanical weed control is not mentioned in the state-of-the-art/IPM improved scenarios of Denmark, Germany and Romania.

Potatoes

For **potatoes**, some important differences were noticed between the different cropping systems. The production of early potatoes requires less intervention tools than the production of warehouse potatoes. This can be explained by their shorter/earlier growing season, resulting in less pest and disease pressure. For example, in Belgium, no *Alternaria* or Colorado beetle (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata*) treatment is necessary in early potato production and less sprayings against late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*) are possible. Even though seed potatoes are also harvested earlier, similar to the early potatoes, they do require more intervention tools than the early potatoes because of the stricter pest and disease tolerance as a result of the certification process. This is also why a longer crop rotation is done with seed potatoes. Denmark is the only country where the majority of the potato farmers already use mechanical weed control and nematode identification techniques.

CROP SPECIFIC INFORMATION

Strawberry

In **strawberry** production, the propagation strategy also requires more chemical inputs than the production strategy. This can be explained by the fact that it is from utmost importance to create clean and healthy starting material, as it serves as the basis for the strawberry production in the next season. In strawberry production on substrate, no herbicides are needed. However, in the full soil production strategy in Spain herbicides are also not used, as the raised beds that are covered with a plastic mulch are sufficient for weed control. In Belgium, both physical barriers and herbicides are necessary to control weeds in full soil systems, highlighting the difference in weed pressure between both countries. The use of natural enemies is already part of the state-of-the-art scenarios in Belgium and the Netherlands. In Spain, this is part of the IPM improved scenario.

Onion

When comparing the state-of-the-art scenarios for spring **onion** sowing in Italy and Poland, the Italian case includes more IPM tools and focuses more on preventive measures and monitoring. In both countries, no tolerant/resistant cultivars and no mechanical weed control are used by the majority of conventional farmers, however, these practices are included in the IPM improved scenarios. In Poland, a larger number of insecticides is used compared to the Italian case. This could be because of the lower amount of preventive tools in the Polish strategy compared to the Italian strategy or because of differences in pest pressure in both countries. A similar number of fungicide and herbicide products are used.

NEXT STEPS

The IPM strategies will further be used in the SUPPORT project by analysing them with the IPM monitoring tool, developed within the project. This will enable an **impact assessment** of the different crop protection strategies regarding pest control efficacy and the economic, environmental and social impact. During several focus groups in the second half of 2025, the results of these impact assessments will be presented and discussed with relevant stakeholders within each NCC, feeding into the development of '**future IPM scenarios**'. These future IPM scenarios will describe the crop protection scenarios in which IPM tools that are currently under development, but expected to be implemented in practice within five years, are being applied in addition to, or as replacement of current IPM tools. The future IPM scenarios will be added to the state-of-the-art and IPM improved scenarios in the Deliverable 4.6 of the SUPPORT project.

For more information, you can consult the full Deliverable 4.5 [here](#).

In case you want to see other relevant deliverables regarding the SUPPORT project, click [here](#).

